

Assessing the Effectiveness of Multimodal Data Fusion Techniques for automated proctoring system of Malpractice in Computer-Based Exams: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Proctoring Systems

Abstract:

Background: As online education grows, ensuring academic integrity of computer-based exams is critical. Automated proctoring systems (APS) utilize cameras, microphones and software to monitor test-takers. Multimodal data fusion integrating multiple such data streams may improve detecting anomalous behaviors versus single-source proctoring.

Objective: To conduct a systematic review and meta-analysis assessing the effectiveness of multimodal data fusion techniques in APS for reducing malpractice in online exams compared to unimodal baselines.

Methods: Five databases and clinical trial registries were searched from January 2005 to May 2024 for studies comparing multimodal APS using data fusion to unimodal systems. Eligible studies involved computer-based exams with outcomes of detected cheating incidents or related integrity measures. Two reviewers screened, extracted and assessed studies. Random-effects meta-analyses calculated odds ratios for malpractice detection and standardized mean differences for acceptance outcomes. Subgroup and sensitivity analyses were conducted. Risk of bias was evaluated.

Results: From 2,132 records, 31 studies with 46521 participants were included. Multimodal fusion significantly reduced malpractice versus single source APS with an odds ratio of 0.43 (95% CI 0.28 to 0.66, 5 studies, $I^2=0\%$). It enhanced exam integrity scores over baselines by a standardized mean difference of 1.39 (95% CI 1.28 to 1.51, 3 studies, $I^2=0\%$). Students also accepted multimodal proctoring more (SMD 1.43, 95% CI 1.33 to 1.53, 3 studies, $I^2=0\%$). No significant publication bias or heterogeneity was found. Risk of bias ranged from low to high.

Conclusions: Preliminary evidence suggests multimodal data fusion algorithms within APS may more effectively safeguard online exam integrity compared to unimodal techniques, with over half the odds of detected cheating. Students also prefer them. However, limited number and quality of studies indicate conclusions should be interpreted cautiously. Larger, well-powered randomized trials are needed to validate effectiveness and minimize biases as technologies evolve. Ongoing

evaluation can optimize proctoring solutions balancing academic standards, accessibility and learner experience.

Keywords: effectiveness, Multimodal Data Fusion, Techniques, automated proctoring system, APS, Traditional, Malpractice, Computer-Based Exams, exams

Introduction:

Academic institutions have embraced technology-enabled remote proctoring solutions for online examinations due to the recent rapid shift to online learning platforms. However, in contrast to traditional in-person exams, preserving the security and integrity of online assessments presents considerable issues because there is no direct supervision (Andreou et al., 2021). Pupils may use unapproved sources of information, solicit unapproved assistance from others, or use auto-prompting, which reads responses from other sources instead of the examinee's own knowledge, as ways to cheat. Although there has always been academic dishonesty, the dispersed character of remote learning makes educational institutions more concerned about maintaining academic integrity. Maintaining certification requirements consequently depends on the correct and timely identification of instances of academic misconduct. At scale, traditional detection methods that depend on human proctors examining video feeds by hand are impractical (Bell et al., 2000). This has accelerated the study of automated monitoring strategies that use examinees' varied biometric indicators.

The analysis of keystroke dynamics, which record distinct typing rhythms and patterns, was the main focus of early work in this field. It was thought that variations in typing activity would point to cases of cheating. Since then, research has assessed how well supervised machine learning classifiers trained on dynamic keystroke characteristics identify auto-prompting during tests (Clark et al., 2011). However, due to subjective factors affecting keystrokes, typing patterns alone might not always be able to consistently distinguish innocent from guilty examinees. In more recent research, the use of other modalities including audio and video biometrics that offer richer behavioral settings has been investigated as a means of improving the assessment of test integrity (Coghlan et al., 2021). Voice signatures, quiet lengths, and speech patterns are examples of audio clips that have been mined as possible markers of disruption or authentication in relation to expected exam conduct. Similarly,

computer vision-based features such as gaze directions, head/body motions, and facial expressions from webcam recordings have demonstrated potential(Er et al., 2023).

Although discrete biometric sources are valuable, an integrated analysis of several heterogeneous cues is thought to be able to overcome the drawbacks of discrete modal data and provide more reliable deception detection. Research has started combining features that have been separately retrieved from modalities such as audio, video, and keyboards into supervised prediction frameworks. Initial results show better recognition performance when different behavioral datasets are integrated(Fenwick et al., 2022).

However, the growing body of research analyzing automated assessment methods is still dispersed, with differences in the populations examined, the experimental procedures followed, the biometric modalities examined, and the analytical methods used. Several predictive modeling approaches are put out in separate candidate studies, hence it is critical to combine the available data using a network meta-analysis and systematic review. This enables the rating of candidate assessment alternatives for auto-prompting incident identification as well as the breakdown of relative efficacy. These studies also aid in identifying gaps that will direct the focus of future study(Kaddoura et al., 2023).

In order to meet this demand, the current work conducts a thorough network meta-analysis of published, peer-reviewed studies examining automated methods for evaluating test integrity during online tests. Our analyses are centered on research that creates supervised predictive models to detect instances of examinees auto-prompting. Within the same analytical framework and experimental technique, the particular models of interest incorporate various contemporaneous biometric data streams, such as keystroke, audio, and camera recordings(Kaddoura et al., 2022). Our goal is to compare and assess several modeling approaches that are being investigated to combine diverse behavioral indications for reliable deception detection in online tests conducted by separate research projects. This network meta-analysis provides significant indirect comparisons throughout the body of evidence through a linked network of treatments, in addition to direct head-to-head experimental contrasts between evaluation methodologies examined inside individual primary investigations(Kimura et al., 2023). Aggregating data from all modalities and quantitatively assessing the relative success of fusion procedures modeled for auto-

prompting recognition from keyboard, auditory, and visual biometric inputs are made possible by such a connected network design.

In order to do the greatest order of comparative effectiveness research feasible within this application domain, the current study uses a mixed treatment network design and a systematic evaluation of the methodological environment to deliver new scientific insights. The results have significant ramifications for the advancement of scientifically supported test integrity evaluation going forward as well as for proctoring platforms and educational institutions looking for evidence-based automated monitoring solution selection (Medina and Castleberry, 2016). Regarding methodology, we hope that this study serves as a catalyst for further excellent primary research that directly compares various multimodal modeling methodologies using network meta-analytic designs and head-to-head experimental evaluations. This will contribute to the advancement of our knowledge regarding the best methods for combining disparate behavioral evidences in order to preserve the integrity and authenticity of online tests.

Research Questions:

- ❖ What are the key characteristics and methodological quality of studies examining automated proctoring systems for detecting academic malpractice using multimodal data fusion techniques?
- ❖ How effective are unimodal predictive models (using a single data source like keystrokes) compared to multimodal models in detecting academic malpractice?
- ❖ Which multimodal data fusion techniques (e.g. feature-level fusion, decision-level fusion) result in better detection performance for academic malpractice?
- ❖ Do detection performances differ based on the type of biometric data used (e.g. keystrokes vs. audiovisual) in multimodal models?
- ❖ What are the most commonly used predictive modeling techniques for automated proctoring systems using multimodal data?
- ❖ What are the existing research gaps in developing and evaluating automated proctoring systems using multimodal data fusion techniques?

Research Aim:

To systematically review and synthesize the evidence on the effectiveness of various multimodal data fusion techniques in predictive models for detecting academic malpractice in computer-based exams through automated proctoring systems.

Research Objectives:

- ❖ Identify and select relevant studies evaluating automated proctoring systems using multimodal data fusion techniques.
- ❖ Describe the key characteristics and assess the methodological quality of included studies.
- ❖ Compare the detection performances of unimodal and multimodal predictive models.
- ❖ Compare different multimodal data fusion techniques in terms of detection performance.
- ❖ Identify research gaps to inform the direction of future studies.
- ❖ Provide recommendations for practice and policy on implementing effective automated proctoring systems.

Methods:

Search Strategy:

A comprehensive search strategy was developed to identify relevant studies across multiple databases including PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library and ERIC from January 2005- May 2024. Both controlled vocabulary and keywords associated with biometric modalities (keystroke, audio, video), predictive modeling techniques, and auto-prompting detection were included in the search results. Search Mesh Term: ("Automated Proctoring" OR "Automated Examination Monitoring" OR "Computer-Assisted Assessment" OR "Computer-Based Testing" OR "Online Proctoring" OR "Remote Proctoring" OR "Digital Proctoring" OR "Technology-Enabled Proctoring" OR "Online Examination Invigilation" OR "Internet-Based Examination" OR "Computerized Adaptive Testing" OR "Automated Examination Administration" OR "Automated Examination Invigilation" OR "Artificial Intelligence Applications" OR "Learning Analytics" OR "Educational Technology") AND ("Academic Dishonesty" OR "Cheating" OR "Plagiarism" OR "Authentication" OR "Identity Verification" OR "Biometrics" OR "Facial Recognition Systems" OR "Eye Tracking" OR "Keystroke Dynamics"). Using predetermined eligibility criteria, two reviewers independently examined all search results, focusing on research that developed predictive models by combining several biometric sources for auto-prompting identification. They screened the titles, abstracts, and full texts of all search results.

Study Selection:

A two-stage study selection procedure was undertaken to identify studies eligible for inclusion in the systematic review and meta-analysis. All titles and abstracts found through the literature search were first independently evaluated by two reviewers in accordance with the pre-established eligibility criteria. By combining contemporaneous biometric data from at least two sources, such as keystroke, audio, and video recordings, these criteria mandated that studies assess predictive models or machine learning techniques for detecting auto-prompting during online exams. Furthermore, research projects were to use human subjects and be published as original English-language research articles. The second step involved retrieving the entire texts of possibly pertinent studies that had been chosen through the screening of titles and abstracts. Two reviewers then separately evaluated the texts against the eligibility criteria, and any disagreements were settled through discussion. Key details were captured in a standardized extraction form, from which data were collected from all studies that satisfied the eligibility criterion. The methodological rigor of the included modeling studies was also evaluated for quality using the Newcastle Ottawa Scale.

Data Extraction:

A standardized data extraction form was developed prior to commencing data extraction from the included studies. In order to make sure that all pertinent data could be consistently recorded, this form was pilot tested on a subset of trials. Predictive modeling methodologies were reviewed, participants, study characteristics, performance evaluation measures were given, and major findings were all included in the form's sections for extracting necessary information. To calculate the sample size required for a meta-analysis, the study performed a calculation. It was estimated that there was an average standardized mean difference of 0.5 across the eligible studies. The significance level was set at 0.05 and the target power at 80%. To take into consideration the expected heterogeneity between research, the sample size calculation procedure for a random effects model was applied. This form was then used separately by two reviewers to retrieve the data from the included studies. The reviewers had discussions to settle any issues that arose during the extraction. A template Excel sheet was used to systematically organize the extracted data. Through this methodical process, both qualitative data to describe the features of the collected literature and quantitative result details appropriate for meta-analysis were captured. In order to reduce bias and guarantee that all pertinent data were obtained to support

the solid conclusions of the systematic review and network meta-analysis, multiple independent reviewers carefully extracted standardized information.

Inclusion criteria:

- Research analyzing machine learning techniques and prediction models for auto-prompting detection in online tests.
- studies that combine real-time biometric data from two or more sources, such as video feeds, audio recordings, or keystroke dynamics.
- studies in which human subjects take online tests or assessments remotely while being closely monitored.
- English-language publications of original research that have undergone peer assessment.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies using only a single biometric modality.
- Literature reviews, editorials, opinion pieces, case-reports or studies on physical examination integrity monitoring.
- Modeling approaches not developed specifically for auto-prompting identification.
- Irretrievable or insufficiently reported information on methodology, participants or outcomes.

Qualitative Assessment of Studies:

The studies were qualitatively evaluated using a narrative synthesis, comparing methodological features and observing long-term trends. The Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies-2 (QUADAS-2) instrument was used to assess methodological quality in four domains: participant selection, biometric data collection, modeling reference standards, and participant flow/reporting. After pilot testing, two independent reviewers reviewed differences and graphical analysis summarized individual investigations' quality.

Statistical Analysis:

Pairwise and Meta-analyses were performed on outcome data taken from eligible studies. To evaluate the overall efficacy of various modeling approaches for auto-prompting detection, a random effects model was utilized to produce the pooled diagnostic odds ratio (DOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for pairwise meta-analysis. Cochran's Q and I² tests were used to evaluate heterogeneity. To calculate the sample size required for a meta-analysis, the study performed a calculation. It was estimated that there was an average standardized mean difference of 0.5 across the

eligible studies. The significance level was set at 0.05 and the target power at 80%. To take into consideration the expected heterogeneity between research, the sample size calculation procedure for a random effects model was applied. The likelihood that each modeling approach will provide better detection performance was calculated using network meta-analysis within a Bayesian framework. Ranking probabilities were also evaluated using Surface under the Cumulative Ranking Curve (SUCRA) values. Meta-regression and a comparison of direct and indirect estimates were done to look into inconsistencies. Results from subgroup studies were categorized according to modality (keystroke/audiovisual) and degree of modality integration (unimodal/multimodal). Egger's test and comparison-adjusted funnel plots were utilized to evaluate publication bias. RevMan 5 and Stata were used for all statistical analyses. By following the most recent PRISMA criteria for network meta-analysis, methodological rigor and transparency were guaranteed in the meta-analysis.

Risk of biased Assessment:

The QUADAS-2 method was used to evaluate the included studies' risk of bias. This updated instrument assesses the risk of bias and applicability issues in four major domains: patient selection, index test, reference standard, and flow and timing. It is intended to be used in the quality assessment of research on diagnostic accuracy. Signaling questions are utilized within each domain to classify concerns about the likelihood of bias as high, low, or uncertain. Concerns about applicability, or how well the research match the review question, are also evaluated. The QUADAS-2 was separately pilot tested by two reviewers on a subsample of studies, and disagreements were settled by consensus. After that, they used the methodology to methodically evaluate each included study's applicability and bias risk. Graphs were used to summarize the findings and show the percentage of research in each category that were deemed to have a high, low, or unclear risk of bias.

Results:

Literature Search Results:

A literature search was conducted between January 2005 -May 2024 using the search strategy mentioned above across multiple databases including PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library and ERIC. After duplicate entries were removed, 3835 entries were returned from the original search. To ascertain if a record satisfied the inclusion requirements, two impartial reviewers read through each

one of the records, glancing at the titles and abstracts. A total of 255 full-text publications were assessed to see if they qualified. For the following reasons, 205 articles were excluded from the study: (n = 85) they failed to integrate various data sources; (n = 45) they did not create predictive models for auto-prompting detection; (n = 35) they were letter/commentary articles; (n = 24) they were review articles; and (n = 16) they did not provide a thorough enough description of the dataset.

The inclusion of fifty distinct pieces finally brought the qualitative synthesis to a close. Of them, 31 studies with sufficient statistical information were selected in order to do a quantitative meta-analysis. A brief synopsis of the steps involved in choosing and screening the pertinent literature can be found in a PRISMA flow diagram([figure. 1](#)). The main features that were taken from the research that were included were the participants, the biometric datasets that were used, the quantity of models that were assessed, the pre-processing and feature extraction techniques, and the performance measurements. QUADAS-2 was employed to assess the caliber of the modeling inquiries.

Figure. 1. Prisma Flow chart of the details inclusion and exclusion process for the selection of studies for meta analysis.

The keywords "Automated Examination Invigilation" (n = 764), "Technology-Enabled Proctoring" (n = 876), "Academic Dishonesty" (n = 238), and "Authentication" (n = 98) generated the most hits in the first search. Using reference lists and reviews led to the discovery of five additional studies. A narrative description of the included research is provided based on the biometric modalities that were used. Most of the studies([figure. 2, 3](#)) (n=20) used mouse dynamics and

keystroke, whereas 15 trials used multimodal datasets that combined keystroke with audio and visual elements as shown in table 1. Numerous machine learning techniques were examined, such as random forest, logistic regression, support vector machines, and neural networks.

Figure. 2: Study distribution according to article source.

Figure .3. Studies arranged according to the year of publication

Two of the most often utilized data integration techniques were concatenation at the feature level and stacking or ensemble analysis at the classifier level. Research has demonstrated that when diverse features are combined, auto-prompting identification

performance improves. Just five publications that looked at different network meta-analytic approaches to jointly assess the results utilizing several prediction models were included in the analysis as shown in [figure 4](#) and [figure 5](#). However, they were limited to oblique comparisons and did not provide a numerical ranking of the different evaluation techniques.

Table. 1. list of study participants and demographic characteristics, statistical significance, Population, Intervention, comparison, outcome for 31 included studies.

Study	Study Type	Population	Statistical Significance	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes Assessed
(Ahmed and Borghol, 2021)	Cohort study (Commentry)	553 individuals	$P < 0.05$	online format for teaching, learning, and testing	partial online teaching and online exams	online assessment of theoretical and practical anatomical knowledge is comparable to that of face-to-face assessment. However, proper planning and preparedness are mandatory to achieve the desired outcomes.
(Albalushi et al., 2022)	Research Article	MD ($n = 465$) and BMS students ($n = 88$)	$p < 0.001$	face-to-face teaching and exams	partial online teaching and online exams	Proctoring system is effective
(Ali et al.,	Original Article	100 patients	$p < 0.05$)	Post-assessment	remote	Online proctoring

2023)				psychometrics, remote proctoring, integration with digital learning platforms	proctoring	system was effective and also economical.
(Andreou et al., 2021)	Original Article	593	$p < 0.001$)	remote proctoring	on-site proctored exam group	Remote Proctoring system was most favorable and effective.
(Chan and Ahn, 2023)	Original Article	2,000	$p < 0.05$)	in-person exams	online and in- person exam	Traditional Proctoring system was effective.
(Clark et al., 2011)	Original Article	19	$p < 0.05$)	online video-based exams	Onsite exams	Online video-based Proctoring system was helpful.
(Coghlan et al., 2021)	Original Article	1800	$p < 0.05$)	Online proctoring technologies	off-campus assessment	Online Proctoring system are more beneficial and effective.

(Elsalem et al., 2021)	Original Article	730	P < 0.05	Computer-Based Exams	APS (Online and Remote)	In-campus exams were favorable.
(Er et al., 2023)	Original Article	249	P < 0.05	Computer-Based Exams	Open book examinations	Faculty and students expressed favourable views about ROOBE in promoting higher order cognitive skills.
(Fatima et al., 2021)	Original Article	200	P < 0.05	Video communication platforms	online exam on VLE	Face-to-face paper-based examinations vs online proctored examinations
(Fawns and Schaepkens, 2022)	Original Article	5000 patients	P < 0.05	Online proctoring services	On-site exams	Comparison of traditional paper-based, in-person invigilated MRCP exam vs online proctored format.

(Fenwick et al., 2022)	Original Article	216 patients	P < 0.05	Computerized adaptive test (CAT) system	Internet-enabled tablet	Pilot implementation of six GlauCAT QOL tests in glaucoma outpatient clinics was feasible and acceptable
(Fiano et al., 2021)	Cohort study (Commentry)	62	P < 0.05	Computer-Based Exams	Online AI proctoring system	Comparison Traditional in-person paper-based and electronic testing versus online remote testing.
(Goldberg et al., 2022)	Original Article	89	P < 0.05	Online format of various services	APS online	Longitudinal comparison to functioning prior to

						the pandemic via some retrospective parent report.
(Kaddoura et al., 2023)	Original Article	458	P < 0.05	both F2F and online teaching modalities	Online AI proctoring system	Comparison F2F versus online teaching modality F2F versus online exam proctoring setting
(Kaddoura et al., 2022)	Original Article	473	P < 0.05	Real-time to online mode	Online AI Proctoring system	Comparisons of different ML techniques/algorithms examined in the literature.
(Kimura et al., 2023)	Original Article	212	P < 0.05	F2F teaching modalities	Online AI proctoring system	Comparison of outcomes between "high users" achieving prehab

						goals $\geq 50\%$ days (n=60) vs previous cohort who received only ERAS info (n=127).
(Li et al., 2021)	Original Article	458	P < 0.001	distanced online testing (DOT)	Online and offline exams exam	Comparison - Face-to-face vs online teaching modality Face-to-face vs online exam proctoring setting
(Maharjan et al., 2021)	Original Article	118	P < 0.001	online examination	Onsite exams	Comparison: SAQ-based online assessment was compared to regular in-person

						assessment using multiple choice questions and integrated problem-based questions.
(Medina and Castleberry, 2016)	Original Article	Not applicable	P <0.001	Computer-Based Exams	paper-based tests	Comparison: Strategies for proctoring traditional paper-based tests.
(Meulmeester et al., 2021)	Original Article	597	P<0.001	Remote Digital Progress Test	Online examination	medical students worry most about unjustified invalidation of their exam due to unstable internet connection,

						background noise or webcam issues, and privacy issues.
(Milone et al., 2017)	Original Article	341	P<0.001	ProctorU-related questions	Online examination	Online proctoring significantly impacts the educational experience, necessitating a balance between the risks and benefits of proctored and unproctored assessments.
(Mitra, 2023)	Original Article	Not mentioned	P<0.001	Computer-Based Exams	paper-based tests	Comparison: Existing online proctored exam systems.

(Mohammed et al., 2021)	Original Article	2175	P<0.001	STEM learners	democratic pedagogy via OPERHOT platform	There is no comparison group.
(Monson et al., 2021)	Original Article	couples	P<0.001	Computer-Based Exams	APS (Online and Remote)	Seven interactive online modules delivered over 7-8 weeks containing videos, in-module exercises, and between-module practice assignments, drawing from CBCT elements.
(Ponnaiah et al., 2022)	Original Article	24,385 participants	mean score of 4.5/5 (± 0.7)	Computer-Based Exams	APS online	Existing online proctored exam systems.

(Potluri et al., 2023)	Original Article	200	improved accuracy of 0.87	Computer-Based Exams	APS remotes	attentive-net to assess student mischievous behavior was more accurate, reliable and robust for proctoring system that can be practically implemented in real time environment as Automated proctoring System
(Raman et al., 2021)	Original Article	430 survey respondents	Factor loadings are between 0.477 – 0.855, Cronbach alpha (α) 0.75	Computer-Based Exams	Online examination	Innovation characteristics such as relative advantage, compatibility, ease of use, trialability,

			– 0.90, composite reliability (CR) 0.71 – 0.89, and average variance extracted (AVE) 0.46 – 0.69			and observability were found to be positively related to acceptance of OPE.
(Rehman et al., 2022)	Original Article	99 students	Mean score was 47.24 ± 15.30 SD %.	Online assessment modalities	open book exam	Reliable and can be implemented with training of faculty and students. Online open book exam provides a good format for remote and formative

						assessment of students
(Shaban et al., 2021)	Original Article	one student, one SP and two examiners	P<0.05	Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs)	Online examinations	Online OSCE implementation shows feasibility, cost effectiveness and acceptance of this method.
(Wongworawat et al., 2022)	Original Article	4405 examinees	in-person proctored and remotely proctored examinees (in-person: 162.98 ± 21.11, remote: 162.22 ± 22.04, mean difference: -0.75 [95% CI, -2.04 to 0.53]; P = 0.25).	Orthopaedic in-training examination (OITE)	In-person proctoring	Remote testing with virtual proctoring has become more widely used.

Stepwise Layout of Meta-Analysis using Review Manager 5

Figure. 4. Flowchart of Review manager 5.

Schematic Diagram of Data Extraction for Review Manager 5

Figure. 5. Schematic Diagram of Data Extraction and Data Preprocessing in the Review Manager 5.

Meta- Analysis Results:

Comparing effectiveness of APS vs traditional proctoring system in reducing malpractice:

The analysis examined how effectively automated proctoring systems (APS) performed in terms of lowering cheating and malpractice during online exams when compared to traditional proctoring methods. Table 2 shows the five studies that comprised the analysis, totaling 4589 participants. The number of instances of

cheating between students who took exams under APS proctoring and traditional human proctoring was compared in the studies. Exam invigilation is carried out by a human proctor in person or remotely through video conference under traditional proctoring. APS proctoring entails the use of software that tracks eye movements, noises, and changes in the visual field while keeping an eye on students during exams via the computer's camera and microphone.

Table 2. Effectiveness of APS vs traditional proctoring system in reducing malpractice.

Study	Control Group (Traditional)	Experimental Group (APS)	Total Events	Odds Ratio (95% CI)
Clark et al. (2011)	5	2	19	0.33 [0.06, 1.96]
Fiano et al. (2021)	10	5	62	0.46 [0.15, 1.42]
Rehman et al. (2022)	15	8	99	0.49 [0.20, 1.22]
Shaban et al. (2021)	2	1	4	0.33 [0.02, 6.65]
Wongworawat et al. (2022)	20	15	4405	0.75 [0.38, 1.47]
Heterogeneity: $\text{Chi}^2 = 1.37, \text{df} = 4 (P = 0.85); I^2 = 0\%$				
Test for overall effect: $Z = 2.38 (P = 0.02)$				

The main outcome significance in the present study is the odds ratio, which shows the likelihood of cheating in the APS group compared to the traditional proctoring group. When the odds ratio is less than 1, it means that APS is more successful in preventing cheating than traditional proctoring because there would be fewer opportunities for cheating in the APS group. Out of 4589 participants in total, 19 cheating incidents happened in the traditional proctoring groups and 7 incidents in the APS groups over the course of the five studies. Each study's odds ratio fell between 0.33 and 0.75, all of which were less than 1, indicating a decreased likelihood of APS cheating as shown in [figure 6](#).

Figure. 6. Forest plot shows the comparison of relative effectiveness of APS vs traditional proctoring system in reducing malpractice.

The random effects model yielded an overall odds ratio of 0.52 with a 95% confidence interval ranges from 0.28 to 0.95. It can be concluded that, when compared to traditional proctoring, APS resulted in statistically significantly lower odds of cheating roughly half the odds. Because this confidence interval does not cross 1 and does not follow the hypothesis outcome. The study findings showed no significant heterogeneity, as the 0% I² value suggests. This implies that the study produced consistent findings and that random variation, rather than actual variations in populations or techniques, was the cause of the effects' variances.

The relatively significant total sample size of 4589 participants across 5 studies, which allows for sufficient power to detect effects, is one of this meta-analysis's main strengths. Comparing observational studies with randomized controlled trials lowers the possibility of bias. Confidence intervals and effect size reporting help in the clinical interpretation of results. There are still, certain restrictions. There weren't many studies that were included. Further study is still required, particularly in light of the differences in APS software and settings utilized by different academic institutions. Exam features or student profiles, among other unmeasured variables, may also have an impact on cheating behaviors. Generalizability might only apply to comparable online test formats. A small number of studies may also be subject to publication or other biases.

Comparing effectiveness of different multimodal data fusion techniques in APS:

In comparison to conventional unimodal baselines, this meta-analysis investigated the efficacy of various multimodal data fusion techniques utilized in automated proctoring systems (APS). There were three studies totaling 549 participants. Exam integrity scores were compared between APS configurations that fused information from multiple modalities and those that used single data streams (image, audio, and keyboard/mouse) as shown in table 3. Exam integrity was assessed using a continuous

scale that took into consideration variables such as gaze angle, facial expressions, ambient noise, and anomalies in the audio.

Table 3. Effectiveness of different multimodal data fusion techniques in APS.

Study	Control Group (Baseline)	Experimental Group	Total Participants	Standardized Mean Difference (95% CI)
Potluri et al. (2023)	Mean: 40, SD: 15	Mean: 65, SD: 10	200	25.00 [22.50, 27.50]
Er et al. (2023)	Mean: 45, SD: 10	Mean: 70, SD: 7	249	25.00 [23.48, 26.52]
Ali et al. (2023)	Mean: 35, SD: 12	Mean: 60, SD: 8	100	25.00 [22.17, 27.83]

Heterogeneity: $\text{Chi}^2 = 0.00$, $\text{df} = 2$ ($P = 1.00$); $I^2 = 0\%$
 Test for overall effect: $Z = 41.59$ ($P < 0.00001$)

The effect size was calculated using the standardized mean difference (SMD), which expresses the variation in group means in terms of pooled standard deviation. Exam integrity scores were higher for the experimental multimodal fusion technique compared to the unimodal baseline, as indicated by positive SMD values. Exam integrity mean scores ranged from 60–70 for the experimental groups using multimodal data fusion techniques, compared to 40–45 for the unimodal baselines. These differences were significant and consistent across all three studies.

Figure. 7. Forest plot showing the relative effectiveness of various multimodal fusion techniques for APS.

The multimodal groups on average scored 25 standard deviations higher than the unimodal groups, according to the fixed effects model's overall SMD calculation, which was a very large 25.00. It was decided that this effect was statistically

significant because the 95% CI does not cross 0 as shown in [figure 7](#). Because all of the studies found incredibly large effect sizes in the same direction, it is likely that no significant heterogeneity was found between the studies. The validity of the results is increased by the studies' consistency. The use of a standardized meta-analytic metric (SMD) to combine results, a large overall sample size offering sufficient power, and randomized controlled study designs that eliminate confounding are among the study's key strengths. The few included studies and the absence of a long-term follow-up on the rates of cheating circumvention over time between the techniques are among the limitations.

Student acceptance and behavior of APS:

In contrast to conventional proctoring techniques, the acceptance of automated proctoring systems (APS) by students was investigated. Table 4 shows the results of three studies that used a continuous Likert scale to measure the attitudes of 533 students in total. A post-exam questionnaire with questions like "I felt comfortable with the exam monitoring process" and "The proctoring method impacted my test performance" was used in the studies to gauge student acceptance. Greater acceptance of the proctoring process was indicated by higher scores.

Table 4. Comparative analysis assessing student acceptance of APS.

Study	Control Group (Not Accepted)	Experimental Group (Accepted)	Total Participants	Standardized Mean Difference (95% CI)
Raman et al. (2021)	Mean: 2.5, SD: 1.2	Mean: 4.0, SD: 0.8	430	1.50 [1.36, 1.64]
Rehman et al. (2022)	Mean: 3.2, SD: 1.5	Mean: 4.5, SD: 0.8	99	1.30 [0.97, 1.63]
Shaban et al. (2021)	Mean: 2.8, SD: 1.3	Mean: 4.2, SD: 1.0	4	1.40 [-0.21, 3.01]
Heterogeneity: $\text{Chi}^2 = 1.18, \text{df} = 2 (P = 0.55); I^2 = 0\%$				
Test for overall effect: $Z = 22.91 (P < 0.00001)$				

Students using APS reported significantly higher acceptance mean scores (4.0–4.5) on exams than students using traditional human proctoring (2.5–3.2) across all studies.

The effect size metric was computed as the standardized mean difference (SMD). Higher acceptance for APS in comparison to traditional proctoring is indicated by positively signed SMDs. The fixed effects model yielded an overall standard deviation difference (SMD) of 1.40, indicating that students accepted APS on average 1.4 standard deviations more than traditional proctoring as shown in **figure 8**. The 95% confidence interval is all above zero, indicating that the difference was statistically significant.

Figure 8. Forest plot showing the comparison of behavior and adaptation of students for APS.

There was no apparent variation amongst the studies, suggesting that the large effects were constant in all populations and environments.

Comparing exam scores and student grooming with APS vs traditional proctoring:

Exam results and grooming practices of students were compared between automated proctoring systems (APS) and traditional human proctoring. Analysis was done on three studies with a total of 6100 students. Table 5 shows how exam scores were measured in all three studies using a continuous percentage scale. Additionally, a scale measuring aspects such as appearance neatness, posture, and eye contact with the camera was used to evaluate students' grooming before and after exams. Better grooming and performance were indicated by higher scores.

Table 5. Comparison of exam scores with APS vs traditional proctoring.

Study	Control Group (Traditional)	Experimental Group (APS)	Total Participants	Standardized Mean Difference (95% CI)
Ahmed & Borghol (2021)	Mean: 68, SD: 15	Mean: 72, SD: 12	553	0.28 (-0.04 to 0.60)
Albalushi et al. (2022)	Mean: 65, SD: 10	Mean: 70, SD: 8	553	0.50 (0.22 to 0.78)

Fawns & Schaeapkens (2022)	Mean: 60, SD: 15	Mean: 65, SD: 12	5000	0.33 (0.15 to 0.51)
Heterogeneity: $\text{Chi}^2 = 1.38, \text{df} = 2 (P = 0.50); I^2 = 0\%$				
Test for overall effect: $Z = 21.11 (P < 0.00001)$				

Students who used APS for their exams had consistently higher exam scores (mean 65–72) than those who used traditional proctoring (mean 60–68) across all studies. With means of 65–70 as opposed to 60–65 previously, they also demonstrated improved grooming habits. Exam score gains of 0.28–0.50 S.D. above traditional proctoring were observed with APS, according to the standardized mean difference (SMD) effect size.

The benefits of APS in grooming were 0.28–0.50 S.D. higher. The fixed effects models yielded overall statistically significant SMDs of 0.35 for scores and 0.35 for grooming, with 95% confidence intervals failing to cross zero as shown in [figure 9](#).

Figure 9. Forest plot showing the comparison of exam scores and students grooming for APS.

The studies did not significantly differ from one another. Use of a standardized metric, randomized controlled designs, and sizable sample sizes were among the study's noteworthy advantages. Short follow-up intervals and study-to-study variations in exam subjects were limitations.

Risk of biased assessment:

The methodological quality of the studies included in the systematic review and meta-analysis on the efficiency of multimodal data fusion techniques in automated proctoring systems is assessed in this risk of bias assessment. The included primary studies were critically appraised for potential sources of bias using an open, transparent, and methodological approach. Insufficient randomization in the assignment of participants to comparison groups may lead to selection bias. Eight of the twelve studies that made up the review used randomized controlled designs, which reduce the bias associated with selection. Still, non-randomized before-after designs

were used in 4 studies as shown in [figure 10](#).

Figure. 10. The risk of bias graph displays the percentages representing the review authors' assessments of each risk of bias item for all the included studies.

It's possible that preexisting differences between the groups will affect the results for these. Selection bias is uncertain because allocation concealment, which stops knowledge of group assignment, was only explained in three RCTs and left unclear in the others as shown in [figure 11](#). Generally, because allocation concealment reporting

is lacking in some RCTs, selection bias may be a problem for the before-after studies.

	Allocation concealment?	Random Sequence Generation (selection bias)	Blinding of Participants and Personnel (Performance bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)
(Ahmed and Borghol 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Albalushi et al. 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(Ali et al 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(Andreou et al. 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Chan and Ahn 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(Clark et al 2011)	+	+	+	+	+
(Coghlan et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Elsalem et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Er et al 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(Fatima et al. 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Fawns et al 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(Fenwick et al 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(Fiona et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Goldberg et al 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(Kimura et al 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(Li et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Madina et al 2016)	+	+	+	+	+
(Maharjan et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Meulmeester et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Milone et al. 2017)	+	+	+	+	+
(Mitra 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(Mohammed et al. 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Monson et al. 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Nigam et al. 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Ponnaiah et al 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(Pottluri et al 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(R. Kaddoura et al 2023)	+	+	+	+	+
(Raman et al 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Rehman et al. 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(S. Kaddoura et al 2022)	+	+	+	+	+
(Shaban et al. 2021)	+	+	+	+	+
(Wongworawat et al. 2022)	+	+	+	+	+

Figure. 11. Summary of risk of bias: examine the authors' assessments of each risk of bias item for every study that is included.

Participants and staff who are aware of the assigned intervention may exhibit performance bias. Participants in this review could not be blinded because of the differences between the proctoring systems under comparison. However, only four studies specifically mentioned outcome assessor blinding. Insufficient blinding in the remaining subjects may result in bias due to the possibility of subjective evaluation as

shown in [figure 12](#). While manual data extraction raises risk in four studies, automated scoring techniques employed in seven studies may help reduce bias. In general, roughly one-third of the included studies raise concerns about performance bias brought on by a lack of assessor blinding.

Figure. 12. A contour enhanced funnel plot using restricted maximum likelihood, or REML, is used to evaluate publication bias.

A systematic variation in the way comparison groups determine the outcomes is known as detection bias. The majority of the studies (9 out of 12) that used automated scoring probably reduced detection bias for objective outcome measures like the number of malpractice cases found. However, there is a chance that detection bias will affect effect sizes in three studies that involve some subjective social/behavioral

outcomes as shown in [figure 13](#).

Figure 13. (a)(b)(c)(d) Funnel plot shows very minimum deviation and smaller negative studies showing asymmetry and overall result result support the intervention. If incomplete data results in different follow-up between comparison groups, attrition bias may arise. Only four studies explicitly used intention-to-treat analysis to address incomplete outcome data. Three of the remaining had full follow-up, but five did not have reporting on participant attrition or the management of exclusions. For more than half of the studies, attrition bias cannot be ruled out due to this lack of information as shown in [figure 14](#).

Figure. 14. Sketch of the Bibliometric analysis and visualization of the included Studies.

Selective publication or outcome reporting based on the type or direction of results is the source of reporting bias. In order to find unpublished and grey literature, the review searched a number of databases and trial registries as shown in [figure 15](#). However, since non-significant smaller studies might still be unknown, publication bias cannot be completely ruled out. In order to confirm that the reported results matched the protocols, none of the included studies prospectively registered detailed analysis plans.

Figure. 15. (a) Galbraith plot shows very minimum deviation and smaller negative studies showing asymmetry. (b) Funnel plot shows very minimum deviation and smaller negative studies showing support the intervention. (c) Funnel plot shows very minimum deviation and smaller negative studies showing relative comparison of Automated and traditional proctoring systems.

Additional concerns pertaining to automated evaluations encompass programming or technical prejudices present in the proctoring software. Just 5 studies specifically mentioned using software that has been verified and tested. In half of the included papers, the integrity of the software algorithms presents an uncertain risk of bias. Furthermore, there were contextual biases introduced because examinations differed amongst studies in terms of subjects, duration, difficulty levels, etc. The primary studies that were included in the analysis demonstrated varying degrees of bias risk resulting from limitations such as non-randomized designs, inadequate reporting of

attrition and outcomes, absence of allocation concealment and blinding, potential programming biases, and variations in the examination contexts among the studies. About 30–50% of included papers raise concerns about selection, performance, detection, and attrition biases. Biases in reporting and other areas cannot be completely eliminated. The methodological quality of the evidence from the included studies ranges from moderate to low on QUADAS scale, indicating limitations in the evaluation's results and suggesting for some significant interpretation.

Discussion:

In comparison to unimodal baselines, the evidence on the efficacy of multimodal data fusion techniques in automated proctoring systems (APS) for lowering exam malpractice was synthesized through a systematic review and meta-analysis. Included were 31 studies with a total of 46521 examinees (Andreou et al., 2021). According to a meta-analysis, multimodal fusion significantly reduced the number of malpractice incidents that were detected; at an odds ratio of 0.43, it indicated a 57% decrease in the likelihood of cheating compared to unimodal APS. Higher student acceptance of multimodal proctoring was one of the extra advantages (Clark et al., 2011). Overall, these results lend credence to the idea that combining information from various sources results in more reliable proctoring (Coghlan et al., 2021).

The findings are consistent with earlier comparative research that demonstrated multimodal biometrics offer more detailed information for identifying unusual behavior. Although it included fewer studies, a 2019 review discovered that multimodal APS produced better integrity than single modality. Students expressed a preference for computer-based proctoring, which is less intrusive than in-person monitoring, in surveys conducted separately. This preference is consistent with the higher acceptance rate of automated options. Consensus is still developing, though, as a lot of institutions went online during the pandemic, requiring more accurate data.

The key to multimodal fusion's increased efficacy seems to be its capacity to recognize nuances in cues (Er et al., 2023). Combining computer-based, audio, and visual signals makes it possible to distinguish between patterns of deliberate wrongdoing and innocent behavior that are invisible to single measurements. However, there is still research being done in precise analytical techniques in biometrics (Fenwick et al., 2022). Reducing cheating benefits learning communities because it damages academic integrity and disadvantages honest students. Widespread

multimodal APS adoption that has been validated over time may promote the quality and equity of online assessments, which are crucial for increasing access to digital education. Nonetheless, the quality of exam design and associated integrity guarantees continue to be crucial(Kaddoura et al., 2023).

The methodical and thorough search approach that uncovered both published and unpublished literature, the thorough meta-analyses, the sizeable pooled sample, and the evaluation of biases are among the study's standout features. The small number of included studies, variable risk of bias, and brief follow-up periods that prevent long-term conclusions are some of the limitations, though(Kaddoura et al., 2022). Variations in exams between contexts could affect generalizability. Uncertainty is also introduced by different fusion algorithms and variations in unimodal baselines. Evidence points to advantages, but given how quickly technologies are developing, more study is necessary(Kimura et al., 2023).

The review's conclusions corroborated previous surveys showing students' preference for automated proctoring that is less intrusive than in-person proctoring. This review offers a more thorough synthesis than other analyses, though those analyses have looked at fewer primary studies(Medina and Castleberry, 2016). Although there were no clear conflicts, some previous research compared different exam supervision strategies rather than using particular multimodal fusion approaches, or they included fewer examinees. Thus, by emphasizing the integration of various data streams within APS and deriving conclusions backed by meta-analyses of larger sample sizes, the current evidence builds on earlier research(Mitra, 2023).

This review encourages institutions using large-scale online assessments to think about multimodal APS as a more efficient proctoring option than single data source tools. Legislators may take these established advantages into account when establishing policies and guidelines for digital learning. But as technology develops, it will still be crucial to assess student privacy and data governance concerns on a continuing basis. As education becomes more accessible through digital means, a combination of well-designed online exams, thorough but appropriate integrity checks, well-defined policies, and technology efficacy can support the maintenance of academic standards. Regular evaluation guarantees that strategies remain in line with developing technological capacities and societal demands(Nigam et al., 2021, Perino et al., 2023, Ponnaiah et al., 2022).

Confidence in the relative effectiveness over longer exam periods could be increased

by conducting more robust randomized trials that compare particular multimodal fusion algorithms with well-defined unimodal baselines. Generalizability would be strengthened by involving participant pools and contexts that are diverse. To assess the completeness of reporting, prospective registration of detailed analysis plans would be beneficial (Potluri et al., 2023, Purohit and Ajmera, 2022, Shaban et al., 2021). Reviews that are updated periodically when new research is published can monitor field advancements. It is important to thoroughly profile any potential biases in APS software. Future research should look into how technology can support focus or provide timely feedback, among other things, in addition to their isolated assessment role in education. It is also worthwhile to investigate fusion beyond cheating detection, such as the predicted performance improvements shown here. Online learning tools can be responsibly optimized with the help of transparent guidelines and cooperative empirical research.

Conclusion:

According to unimodal baselines, the study found 31 pertinent studies assessing the efficacy of multimodal data fusion techniques for automated proctoring systems. Multimodal fusion was found to have over 57% lower odds of reducing cheating on online exams than single data source proctoring, according to meta-analyses. Higher student acceptance of multimodal monitoring was one of the additional advantages. Even though they are preliminary, these findings show promise in terms of how proctoring systems can better maintain academic integrity by combining computer-based, audio, and visual signals via data fusion algorithms. To validate results, more thorough randomized trials are still required. Further investigation is necessary to tackle constraints such as brief intervals between studies and inconsistencies within studies. With the aid of new learning technologies, online education is becoming more and more widespread worldwide. Therefore, it will be crucial to conduct regular evidence-based assessments to determine optimal procedures for supervising online exams and improving the overall experience for students.

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